

Unprecedented Concentration Dependent Chemical Shift Variation in ^1H NMR Studies : A Problem in Structure Elucidation and the Study of Molecular Recognition†

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Our studies show that changes in concentration can lead to significant changes in the chemical shifts of nonexchangeable hydrogens, and thus, in the ^1H NMR spectra. An important observation, as described for quinoline and other aromatic compounds, is that different protons shift to different extents in the same solvent as the concentration of the solute is varied, leading to overlap/coalescence or crossover of proton signals. Chemical shift variations can sometimes be so pronounced that they lead to misleading 1D and 2D spectral signatures. Such concentration dependent spectral pattern changes have far reaching implications in the use of ^1H NMR spectroscopy for structure elucidation, spectral characterization, determination of purity and the study of molecular recognition. Our studies further show that chemical shift values obtained by theoretical calculations should be used with caution.

The conventional practice in the elucidation of structural features of a molecule usually involves recording and interpreting its ^1H NMR spectrum in addition to other spectroscopic and analytical studies. However, examination of the NMR spectrum of a molecule as a function of its concentration is seldom done. We have found that the chemical shifts of different nonexchangeable protons change remarkably as the concentration of the molecule (solute) is varied¹. Sometimes, the chemical shift variations are so pronounced that they lead to 1D and 2D spectral signatures that may be misleading. Lack of consideration of the importance of such concentration effects can also lead to unwanted controversies in the design of self-replicating systems².

In view of the exceptional importance of the use of NMR spectra as a tool for structure elucidation, spectral characterization, determination of purity and in the study of molecular recognition, we sought to carefully examine the ^1H NMR spectra of a range of small organic molecules in a number of solvents. We report the evidence of an exceptionally large concentration dependencies in the chemical shifts of various nonexchangeable protons in a given molecule in a variety of solvents commonly used in NMR experiments. We observe that different nonexchangeable protons shift to different extents and can result in coalescence³, overlap, or complete crossover of signals, thus changing the spectrum. Such coalescence or overlap of signals also leads to loss of connectivity in the ^1H - ^1H COSY spectra. Although solvent, concentration, and temperature dependent chemical shift changes are known⁴⁻⁶, such as the well known concentration dependent chemical shift changes of exchangeable hydrogens⁶, concentration dependent chemi-

cal shift changes which lead to crossover or coalescence of ^1H NMR signals¹ of nonexchangeable hydrogens in the same solvent have not been reported⁶. These changes may not be solely due to aromatic solvent induced shifts (ASIS) at least in dilute solutions (*vide infra*), simple dimerization or conventional π - π stacking of solute molecules.⁵ We have studied 20 different compounds to verify the generality of such phenomenon.

Results and Discussion

As a representative example we first discuss the ^1H NMR spectra⁷ of the electron-poor quinoline 1 molecule, measured in CDCl_3 , a weakly hydrogen bond donating solvent ($\epsilon = 4.70$, $\mu = 1.87$)⁸. We observed that the chemical shifts of the quinoline hydrogens are concentration dependent and change to different extents (Figs. 1 and 2). The change in the chemical shift of 4-H ($\Delta c = 4.22$, $\Delta\delta = -0.375$)⁹ is the largest, leading to an overall change in the spectrum by its crossover of 8-H (Fig. 1) at $\sim 0.5 M$. It is interesting to note that, contrary to the common belief, sometimes a better dispersed spectra is obtained at a higher solute concentration (Fig. 1, e.g. spectra taken at 1.06 M vs 0.13 M; Fig. 8, e.g. spectra taken at 1.06 M vs 0.066 M). The 4-H and 8-H signals also cross (Fig. 3) at 2.75 M in CD_3CN , a weakly hydrogen bond accepting solvent (Table 1) and at 3.37 M in CD_3OD , a hydrogen bonding solvent. In DMSO- d_6 , a hydrogen bond accepting solvent, there is no crossover and the chemical shift changes are positive between 0 and 2.0 M concentrations. In the nonpolar solvent CCl_4 , the 4-H and 8-H coalesce and could be mistaken as a two-proton doublet at concentrations below 0.13 M. In other nonpolar

†Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

Fig. 1. ¹H NMR spectra of quinoline in CDCl₃ at different concentrations (M). The numbers on the signals refer to the hydrogen atoms.

Fig. 2. Chemical shift (δ , ppm) vs concentration (M) for the protons of quinoline.

solvents like cyclohexane-d₁₂ (8-H, $\Delta c = 4.11$, $\Delta\delta = +0.13$, 4-H, $\Delta\delta = -0.164$) and benzene-d₆ ($\Delta c = 4.11$, 8-H, $\Delta\delta = +0.077$; 4-H, $\Delta\delta = +0.165$), these signals also change to different extents with concentration, but do not crossover. The concentration dependent chemical shift changes in benzene-d₆ are similar to those in the nonaromatic solvent DMSO-d₆ and show positive slopes. These findings indicate that these concentration dependent shifts are not solely due

Fig. 3. Concentration dependent crossover of 8-H and 4-H of quinoline in different solvents.

to aromatic solvent induced shifts (ASIS).

The observed concentration dependent chemical shift changes are different from those caused by paramagnetic shift reagents and temperature changes. In the presence of the shift reagent, Eu(thd)₃, the chemical shifts of the 2-H and 8-H of quinoline, which are proximal to the coordinating nitrogen, move to higher ppm values with increasing concentrations of the shift reagent (Fig. 4). In the absence of shift reagents, the 2-H and 8-H of quinoline show insignificant chemical shift changes as the concentration of quinoline is increased (Fig. 1). On the other hand, the 4-H signal changes most significantly with temperature. With an increase in temperature, we would expect that the chemical

TABLE 1—SOLVENT PARAMETERS*

Solvent	Dielectric constant	Dipole moment	Volume susceptibility
	ϵ	μ	$-\chi_v \times 10^6$
CHCl ₃	4.70	1.87	0.735
CH ₃ CN	36.2	3.92	0.534
CH ₃ OH	32.6	1.70	0.515
CCl ₄	2.23	0	0.684
DMSO	49	3.96	
CH ₂ Cl ₂	8.9	1.60	0.738
Cyclohexane	2.02	0	0.631

*Ref. 8.

Fig. 4. ^1H NMR spectra of quinoline in CDCl_3 (0.29 M) with increasing concentration of the shift reagent, $\text{Eu}(\text{thd})_3$, europium tris(2,2,6,6-tetramethyl-3,5-heptadienoate).

shift changes should parallel dilution. However, the observed shifts are opposite. The 4-H moves to lower ppm values with increasing temperature (Fig. 5) in a manner opposite to those observed for dilution (Figs. 1–3).

π - π stacking has been attributed to be one of the causes of chemical shift changes¹⁰. However, the role of concen-

Fig. 5. Temperature dependent ^1H NMR chemical shifts of 4-H and 8-H of quinoline (0.29 M) in CDCl_3 .

tration on the extent and nature of π - π stacking is not clear. Consequently, substituted quinolines were studied to examine the effect of substituents on π - π stacking, if any, on the concentration dependent chemical shift changes. Methylquinolines showed concentration dependent chemical shift changes. The change in the chemical shift of 4-H of 6-methylquinoline **2** in CDCl_3 is the greatest ($\Delta c = 3.70$, $\Delta\delta = -0.377$) and at $\sim 0.6\text{ M}$ not only do the 4-H and 8-H cross over, but the 5-H and 7-H cross over as well (Fig. 6). The chemical shifts of the nonaromatic methyl (benzylic) hydrogens of methylquinolines also change. The methyl hydrogens of 4-methylquinoline show the greatest shift ($\Delta c = 4.223$, $\Delta\delta = -0.464$).

Fig. 6. Chemical shift (δ , ppm) vs concentration (M) of 6-methylquinoline in CDCl_3 . 2-H showed only very small shifts ($\delta = 8.78$ at 0.015 M and $\delta = 8.71$ at 1.81 M) and is not included in this plot

The 6- and 8-*tert*-butylquinoline¹¹ were studied to check the effect of a bulky group on conventional face to face π - π stacking on concentration dependent chemical shift changes. The trend in the changes of chemical shifts of ring hydrogens in both 6- and 8-*tert*-butylquinoline are similar to those observed in quinoline and in 6- and 8-methylquinoline. In 6-*tert*-butylquinoline, the 4-H ($\Delta c = 1.17$, $\Delta\delta = -0.112$) and 8-H ($\Delta c = 1.17$, $\Delta\delta = +0.024$) also cross over at $\sim 0.73\text{ M}$, indicating that the bulky *tert*-butyl group exerts little effect on the chemical shift changes. Therefore, conventional π - π stacking, if any, does not have effect on the concentration dependent chemical shift changes.

The electronic effect of substituents on concentration dependent chemical shift changes was next studied using an electron-donating methoxy group. In 6-methoxyquinoline

Fig. 7. Chemical shift (δ , ppm) vs concentration (M) of 6-methoxyquinoline in CDCl_3 . 2-H showed only very small shifts ($\delta = 8.85$ at $0.015 M$ and $\delta = 8.78$ at $1.81 M$) and is not included in this plot.

3, the 4-H and 8-H cross $\sim 0.5 M$ in CDCl_3 and 3-H and 7-H coalesce at low concentrations (Fig. 7). The nonbenzylic methoxy protons of 6-methoxyquinoline also shift ($\Delta c = 3.60$, $\Delta\delta = -0.28$). Changing the electron density of quinoline by protonating the nitrogen with TFA (1 : 1 mixture) also caused the quinoline protons to shift with concentration. In this case, the 3-H signal shifted the most ($\Delta c = 0.87$, $\Delta\delta = 0.082$), whereas the 3-H of quinoline, over a similar concentration range showed an opposite shift ($\Delta c = 0.93$, $\Delta\delta = -0.103$).

Electronic effects on concentration dependent chemical shift changes were also investigated in other ring systems. In electron-rich acridine¹² 4, 9-H ($\Delta c = 2.103$, $\Delta\delta = -0.453$), which is equivalent to 4-H in quinoline ($\Delta c = 2.103$, $\Delta\delta = -0.230$) shifts the most in CDCl_3 . The 4-H/5-H ($\Delta c = 2.103$, $\Delta\delta = -0.352$) and 2-H/7-H signals ($\Delta c = 2.103$, $\Delta\delta = -0.170$) cross over at ($2.12 M$) in CDCl_3 . In CD_3OD , the

4-H/5-H signal moves ($\Delta c = 2.103$, $\Delta\delta = -0.499$) from the 2-H/7-H signal and coalesces with the 1-H/8-H signal (Fig. 8).

In indoles¹³ 5, another electron-rich system, 2-H and 7-H shift dramatically ($\Delta c = 3.71$; 2-H, $\Delta\delta = -0.376$; 7-H, $\Delta\delta = -0.383$). The 7-H signal crosses over and the 2-H coalesces with 4-H, 5-H, 6-H multiplet. It is very interesting to note that these shifts are so dramatic that the connectivity in COSY spectrum is lost at lower concentrations of indole. Benzofuran^{13b} 6, an oxygen containing system, also showed chemical shift changes with concentration ($\Delta c = 4.26$; 2-H, $\Delta\delta = 0.211$; 3-H, $\Delta\delta = 0.222$). Naphthalene¹⁴, a nonpolar electron-rich system, showed small concentration dependent chemical shift changes in CDCl_3 ($\Delta c = 2.977$; 1-H, $\Delta\delta = -0.137$; 2-H, $\Delta\delta = -0.132$). In contrast, the electron-poor 1-fluoronaphthalene 7 showed larger chemical shift changes ($\Delta c = 2.977$; 4-H, $\Delta\delta = -0.193$; 8-H, $\Delta\delta = -0.193$). Similarly, the ^1H NMR of the electron-poor molecule isoquinoline¹⁵ 8 showed significant shifts with concentration in CDCl_3 ($\Delta c = 4.223$; 4-H, $\Delta\delta = -0.262$; 8-H, $\Delta\delta = -0.303$), and in cyclohexane- d_6 , the 4-H crosses the 6-H at a higher concentration ($\sim 4.24 M$) and the 7-H at a lower concentration ($\sim 0.13 M$).

Since we have examined this phenomena in a range of solvents including H-bond donors and acceptors, polar and nonpolar solvents, protic and aprotic solvents as well as hydrocarbons, the present observations do not originate from classical⁴ solvent induced effects. We have also found that these solvent dependent concentration dependent chemical shift changes are quite different from chemical shift changes resulting from shift reagents and temperature variation.

Solvent dependent changes in liquid/solution structures¹⁶ of compounds, might also manifest themselves in other spectral properties, such as $^3J_{\text{H-H}}$ coupling constants⁴, ^{13}C -NMR chemical shifts and ^1H longitudinal relaxation times. Preliminary observations show that there are insignificant changes ($< 0.05 \text{ Hz}$) in the proton ($^3J_{\text{H-H}}$) coupling constant values of the compounds studied with changes in concentration. In addition, the ^{13}C chemical shift changes of quino-

line with change in concentration are small (1–2 ppm) and do not result in a spectral pattern change. The ^1H longitudinal relaxation times (T_1 in s) for the various protons decrease with increasing concentrations of quinoline, but to different extents for different protons¹⁷. These changes in T_1 value do not parallel the corresponding concentration

Fig. 8. ^1H NMR spectra of acridine in CD_3OD at different concentrations (M). The numbers on the signals refer to the hydrogen atoms.

dependent changes in the chemical shifts.

Why there is such a dramatic concentration dependent variation in the chemical shift values of protons, leading to crossover and coalescence of signals is not known. Although, the chemical shift of a nuclei is a function of the electron density in the immediate vicinity, the shielding and deshielding effect as a function of solvent concentration has not been studied to a great extent. The effect of solute concentration on the solute-solute, solute-solvent and solvent-solvent interaction is known but has not been related to changes in chemical shifts. Molecules with extended conjugation are known to undergo π - π stacking. There are different types of stacking depending on the nature of the molecules¹⁰. Several attempts in the past have been made to understand the interactions as a result of stacking of simple aromatic systems¹⁸. The nature of stacking in molecules like quinoline, if any, has not yet been reported. We have, thus, attempted to understand the nature of intermolecular interactions in simple dimeric and trimeric clusters of simple organic molecules like quinoline and indole, and if possible,

their effect on the ^1H chemical shift values. To this effect we did modeling¹⁹ of quinoline interactions and also performed *ab initio* calculations.

A model was developed based on the electrostatic/Coulombic interaction between two quinoline molecules in the simplest case. The charges on these molecules were determined by EHMO calculations¹⁹. The 'parallel' structure (face to face π - π stacking) of two molecules of quinoline (Fig. 9) with an antiparallel arrangement of the dipoles was obtained from molecular mechanics energy minimization using the Coulombic interactions by the MM2 force field as supplied in HyperChem (version 5.02)¹⁹.

Fig. 9. The structure of quinoline dimers, face to face π - π stacking.

The interaction of two quinoline molecules was also determined using *ab initio* calculations. The T-shaped structure (Fig. 10) was obtained as a minimum from a restricted Hartree-Fock calculation with full geometry optimization using at 3-21G* basis set and the Gaussian 94 suite of programs²⁰.

We have calculated the ^1H NMR spectra using the software in HyperNMR²⁰. The calculated spectra is quite different from the observed spectra. Although, we have made other attempts to calculate¹⁹ the chemical shifts of the protons in the cluster, the values are quite different from the experimental values (Table 2).

Current methods available for calculating chemical shift values of protons do not routinely include the solvent pa-

rameters and thus the role of the solvent. Any spectral measurement is a time averaged macroscopic property of the molecule in a bulk medium, whereas the theoretical calculations are done on a single molecule in the gas phase at a temperature of zero Kelvin. None the less, such calculations, done for ideal situations, should give some insight into the microscopic solution structure of the aggregate.

Chemical shift changes due to solute-solvent/solvent-solvent interactions,²¹ host-guest complexation²² and hydrophobicity of organic molecules²³ have been reported in

Fig. 10. The structure of quinoline dimers, T-shaped structure.

the literature. Although chemical shift changes due to the stacking of DNA/RNA bases in helical structure²⁴ have been reported, such chemical shift changes may be due to the changes in the conformation of these molecules at different concentrations. Obviously in our case, chemical shift changes are not taking place due to changes in conformation (with concentration) of molecules. Chemical shift changes due to concentration dependent intramolecular conformational

TABLE 2—OBSERVED AND CALCULATED CHEMICAL SHIFT VALUES OF QUINOLINE PROTONS

Protons	2H	3H	4H	5H	6H	7H	8H
6-311++G (2d, 2p) ^a	9.4989	7.4389	8.4425	8.0657	7.7973	8.0593	8.3669
6-311G (d, p) ^a	9.6596	7.5531	8.5830	8.2034	7.9570	8.1965	8.4507
Observed ^b	8.9357	7.4187	8.1804	7.8363	7.5621	7.7357	8.1195

^aNorth Carolina Super Computer Center, Gaussian 94, Version B.2.

^bAt very low concentration in CDCl₃.

changes in the rigid systems that we have studied are impossible. The dramatic variation of the chemical shifts observed in the present study could be a consequence of molecular aggregation leading to the formation of differently packed supramolecular assemblies. In such assemblies, the number of molecules, the orientations in the aggregate and their mutual interactions and 'tightness' of association should vary as a function of concentration which in turn should manifest in the altered chemical shifts. Lack of the consideration of the importance of concentration effects in the study and thus design of self-replicating systems have led to unwanted controversies².

Our observations of such pronounced variation of chemical shifts as a function of concentration is hitherto not reported in the literature. It is obvious that the implications of such findings are extremely significant, given the resurging interest in the use of NMR spectroscopy for the determination of binding constants in molecular recognition phenomena. In these studies a solution of a guest molecule is added in incremental amounts to a solution containing the host. The observed changes in the chemical shifts of the highest affected proton is plotted against concentration of the host in a typical molecular recognition experiment for the determination of the association constant and the stoichiometry of binding between the host and the guest. However, verification of any changes in the chemical shift as a function of concentration of either the host or the guest is not done. In view of the findings presented in this communication, it is clear that such conclusions on the binding strength and nature of association could often be very misleading, if not incorrect².

One may conclude from the foregoing experiments that the concentration of the molecule under study has an important bearing on the kind of NMR signature it produces. Such changes in spectral pattern become even more important in view of the fact that higher sample concentrations are required for spectra taken at lower external magnetic field strengths²⁵. Therefore, lack of consideration of the concentration of the NMR sample could lead to incorrect conclusions pertaining to the structural identity of a given molecule. It is also apparent that interpretations pertaining to host-guest binding involving pronounced changes in concentration could result in grossly conflicting or misleading conclusions. It is thus, important to give the solute concentration when reporting NMR spectra²⁶.

Experimental

All spectra were taken on a Bruker AM-300 spectrometer, operating at 300.13 MHz Larmor frequency for proton and at 291 K temperature. All assignments were checked by homonuclear decoupling and ¹H-¹H COSY experiments.

The T_1 values were measured in CDCl_3 by the inversion recovery method. Our studies showed that the chemical shift of the CHCl_3 (in CDCl_3) signal, as well as other solvent signals, change with concentration. Consequently, in all cases the TMS signal was taken as the reference.

Quinoline and isoquinoline were freshly distilled over CaH_2 under argon. The 6- and 8-*tert*-butylquinolines were synthesized from 4- and 2-*tert*-butylanilines respectively, using the Skraup's quinoline synthesis method¹¹. The details of this synthesis will be published elsewhere.

Variable temperature studies were made at two different concentrations, 0.29 and 1.06 M in CDCl_3 from 265.2 to 314.2 at 5 K increments. ^1H NMR spectra of 1.06 and 0.29 M quinoline solutions in CDCl_3 were taken with different amounts of Resolve-Al (Aldrich), $\text{Eu}(\text{thd})_3$, europium tris(2,2,6,6-tetramethyl-3,5-heptadienoate) [CAS Registry number : 15522-71-1].

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 25. These observations have been made irrespective of the external magnetic field strength (B_0). ^1H NMR spectra of various compounds were also measured at 90 MHz on a JEOL spectrometer at UNCW, NC, and at 500 MHz on a Bruker Avance-DRX spectrometer at the Department of Chemistry, Columbia University, NY.
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